

SCALABILITY OF AERODYNAMICS FROM DEMONSTRATOR TO FULL FLIGHT SCALE OF A VERTICAL LANDING REUSABLE LAUNCHER

Ansgar Marwege, Pawel Goldyn, Josef Klevanski, Ali Gülhan
DLR Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology
Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies
Linder Hoehe, 51147 Cologne, Germany
Ansgar.Marwege@dlr.de

ABSTRACT

In the last decade, the vertical landing of launcher first stages has gained large interest due to the successes of SpaceX with its Falcon 9.

In this context, the SALTO (reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations) project, funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme, is supporting the ESA Themis programme in which a demonstrator for a vertically landing launcher first stage is built. A first version for this demonstrator is propelled by one Prometheus engine with about 120 t thrust and performs simple trajectories. This version is called T1H, where the H stands for the “Hop Test” to be performed. A later version, called the Themis 3 or T3, shall have 3 engines and perform more complex flight trajectories. In SALTO the Hop Test of T1H is performed and technologies for the T3 vehicle are matured.

DLR has various tasks in the scope of the SALTO project. One of them is the investigation of the scalability of the technologies developed for the demonstrator to full-scale flight vehicles. This paper will focus on the scalability of aerodynamics between vehicle sizes, e.g. if the grid fins are designed for the trajectory of a specific demonstrator - are these grid fins then representative for a full-scale flight vehicle; are the flying qualities of the complete launcher configurations comparable; etc.

For this purpose, two preliminary full-scale launcher configurations have been designed based on the same technologies as used in the SALTO project (mainly the same Prometheus engines and the same assumptions for these). In this context, a DLR in-house toolset named AIOLOS has been used for the preliminary launcher design. The toolset had been developed partly in scope of SALTO, with the aim of considering the launcher reusability already in the first launcher design loop; this has been achieved by expanding the existing launcher design mathematical model for a general reusable or expendable launch vehicle. Based on these full-scale launcher configurations, in this paper, the aerodynamic similarity parameters, the aerodynamic design, and the aerodynamic modelling approaches are compared between the full-scale launcher configurations and the T3 demonstrator.

Index Terms— *Reusable Launch Vehicle, Retro-Propulsion, Vertical Landing, Future Launcher Configurations, SALTO*

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the first successful landing of the Falcon 9 first stage of SpaceX the reusability approach of landing a first stage vertically has gained great interest in Europe.

In this context the SALTO (reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations) project which is funded in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme, is supporting the ESA Themis programme in which a demonstrator for a vertically landing launcher first stage is built. In Fig. 1 the three scenarios investigated in SALTO are sketched.

The T1H demonstrator is propelled by one Prometheus engine with about 120 t thrust and performs simple trajectories. A hop test of this configuration will be performed in the frame of SALTO.

Furthermore, the T3 vehicle is investigated in detail (see Fig. 2). This is the reference configuration of a more complex demonstrator with three Prometheus engines which could follow the T1H in the future and which would be able to perform more complex trajectories of altitudes of about 80 to 100 km altitude, including all relevant flight phases of the vertical descent and landing approach, which are the re-entry burn, the aerodynamic phase and the landing burn. For the T3 vehicle the aerodynamics, aerothermodynamics, flight dynamics and control laws, structures and TPS are studied. This configuration is discussed in more detail in refs. [1-5].

The future launcher configurations aim to rebuild future European launchers which could descend and land vertically. The configurations are correlated with the T1H and T3 vehicle as closely as possible. Thus, sharing the same engines and the same geometry where possible. This shall enable a direct comparison of the demonstrator with these configurations and shall help to understand how the technologies developed for the demonstrator scale up to full-scale launchers.

In this paper the future launcher configurations are discussed in detail and are compared to the T3 demonstrator. First, the methodology is described. Then, the launcher configurations

are laid out in detail. Finally, the similarity parameters and trajectories of the configurations are discussed and compared to T3.

Fig. 1: Sketch of scenarios investigated in SALTO

Fig. 2: Aeroshape of T3

2 METHODOLOGY

The engine data used in this paper was computed by DLR with the help of the commercially available Rocket Propulsion Analysis (RPA) tool [6], based on publicly available data.

The preliminary design of the future launcher configurations in SALTO was performed following the launcher design loop shown in Fig. 3 and described in ref. [7]. The geometry, masses, dimensions and the overall launcher design were computed with the DLR in-house tool AIOLOS (Adjustable Initial Object-oriented Launcher Optimisation System). It was newly developed in SALTO especially for the design of reusable vertically landing launchers, where the decent fuel and structure necessary for the reusability (e.g. grid fins and landing legs) are already considered in the first preliminary design loop. The tool is described in detail in ref. [7].

The aerodynamics for the ascent phase were computed with the semi-empirical tool CAC (Calculation of Aerodynamic Coefficients) [8]. For the aerodynamics for the descent trajectory, datasets of a re-entering and descending first stage available at the DLR from the RETPRO project [9, 10] were used.

The trajectory was computed with STRATOS (Staged Rocket Trajectory Optimization and Simulation) [11] which is a DLR in-house Python tool based on the long-heritage TOSCA tool, but rewritten in Python in order to make the tool more versatile and better adaptable for specific requirements of vertically landing launchers.

Fig. 3: Launcher Design Loop [7]

The T3 trajectory, which the future launcher configurations are compared too, was provided by Ariane Group. Some additional values as e.g. the thrust along the trajectory and the thrust coefficient were computed based on DLR computations and assumptions.

3 FUTURE LAUNCHER CONFIGURATION STUDIED IN SALTO

Fig. 4 shows the configurations presented by a consortium around Ariane Group in the ESA NESTS Study (New European Space Transportation Solutions) [12, 13]. In SALTO, the future launcher configurations build on the MEDIUM and the HEAVY configuration of this study (see Fig. 4). This is meaningful as these configurations use

Prometheus engines in the first and the second stage. With this, the same baseline assumptions for the engines can be taken as for the T3.

The two configurations studied are:

- MEDIUM Launcher
 - First Stage:
5 Prometheus (adapted for sea level)
 - Second Stage:
1 Prometheus (adapted for vacuum)
- HEAVY Launcher
 - First Stage:
9 Prometheus (adapted for sea level)
 - Second Stage:
1 Prometheus (adapted for vacuum)

Fig. 4: MEDIUM and HEAVY Launcher Configurations as in ref. [14]

3.1 Prometheus Engine (DLR rebuild)

The Prometheus engine was rebuilt by DLR with the help of the commercially available Rocket Propulsion Analysis (RPA) tool [6], for which the input was based on publicly available data.

The assumptions to rebuild the engine are based on the data provided in [15]. However, in ref. [16] it was stated that the thrust of the engine is supposed to be increased from 100 t to 120 t in the future. The pressure in the combustion chamber was given to be 100 bar in [15]. The pressure in the combustion chamber of the Vulcain 2 engine is around 117.3 bar [17]. Hence, it is likely that there is a margin of around 20 bar in the pressure in the combustions chamber which could be used to increase the thrust if a similar combustion chamber as in the Vulcain 2 engine would be used for the Prometheus engine.

Therefore, it was assumed that the thrust of the engine is increased from 100 t to 120 t simply by an increase of the pressure in the combustion chamber. The expansion area ratio was assumed to be 20.

This value is a trade-off between minimizing pressure losses at sea level conditions and, thus, increasing performance at lift-off; maximizing performance in higher atmospheres, and the ability to throttle the engine to low thrust values during landing.

The expansion area ratio of the upper stage engine was chosen to be 100. This is a trade-off of maximizing the vacuum specific impulse (I_{sp}), as this engine operates at high altitudes, and limiting its size. Fig. 5 depicts the I_{sp} of the engine over the expansion area ratio, showing that the value of 100 is a reasonable value, as for higher expansion area ratios the slope of the curve is tailing off.

The properties of the engines are summarized in Tab. 1.

Fig. 5: Vacuum Isp over Expansion Area Ratio for DLR Prometheus engine

Engine	Lower Stage Engine	Upper Stage Engine
Characteristics	Adapted for sea level	Adapted for vacuum – 100 as a good compromise
Fuel	LCH4/LOX	LCH4/LOX
Oxidizer Fuel Ratio (OFR)	3.5	3.5
Expansion Area Ratio	20	100
Chamber Pressure	120 bar	120 bar
Exit Pressure	0.756 bar	0.094 bar
Exit Diameter	1.2 m	2.68 m
Isp Vacuum	355.04 s	384.83 s
Isp Sea Level	323.19 s	225.59 s
Thrust Vacuum	1259.287 kN	1312.668 kN
Thrust Sea Level	1146.319 kN	800.142 kN

Tab. 1: Summary of engine properties of DLR Prometheus engine version

3.2 MEDIUM configuration

The MEDIUM configuration with 5 Prometheus engines in the first stage and 1 Prometheus engine in the second stage resulted in the design as detailed in Tab. 2. The definitions of the launcher parameters are as given in ref. [7]. The mass distribution is shown in Fig. 7.

The configuration can be summarized as follows:

- Design Payload: 16.24 t to LEO (200 km)
- Payload to GTO: 0.92 t (estimated)
- Gross Lift-off Weight (GLOW): 483.74 t
- Thrust to Weight Ratio: 1.2
- Structural fraction dry
 - 6.8 % – stage 1
 - 7.4 % – stage 2

Fig. 6 shows the ascent trajectory of the MEDIUM configuration. It is noticeable that the stage separation is at a relatively low altitude of 58 km, at a separation velocity of 1.625 km/s and at a Mach number of 5.1. The dynamic pressure is 512 Pa. For T3 it was shown in ref. [2] that stability problems can occur for the first stage after stage separation if the stage separation is at low altitudes. As the dynamic pressure is large enough to turn the vehicle due to aerodynamic forces, but no control with the thrust vector control is achievable anymore. However, the low stage separation altitude and low velocity at stage separation can also be advantageous as it leads to reduced dynamic pressure and heat loads in the descent phase (see section 4.2). Therefore, it will be studied in SALTO if these stability problems could be an issue for the MEDIUM configuration. The outline of the MEDIUM first stage is shown in Fig. 8. The outer diameter of the configuration was selected to be 4.5 m. Then the T3 aeroshape (see Fig. 2) was scaled to fit to this diameter. However, as the tank volume was too small and too much empty space was left, the configuration was slightly shortened to a length of 30.9 m, excluding the interstage. The close resemblance of the geometries of MEDIUM and T3 make the aerodynamic coefficients and aerodynamic databases generated for both configurations in SALTO very comparable.

Fig. 6: Ascent trajectory of MEDIUM configuration

	Stage1	Stage2
Mass ratio	2.39707	5.40544
Stage mass share	0.669972	0.296458
Δv_i	2952.89	6368.09
Mass	324094	143409
Mass propellant ascent	281848	130114
Mass propellant descent	14092.4	0
Mass propellant total	295940	130114
Mass propellant reserve	2959.4	1301.14
Mass propellant dead	5918.8	2602.28
Mass payload	159649	16239.1
Mass gross real	483542	159552
Mass structure real wet	42246.1	13295.1
Mass structure real dry	22034.7	10596.5
Mass structure margin	2203.47	1059.65
Structural frac. real wet	0.130352	0.0927077
Structural frac. real dry	0.0679885	0.0738901
Height	30.9699	26.3725
Outer diameter	4.5	4.5
Thrust (vacuum)	6108160	1312670
Thrust (sea level)	5731600	---
Thrust to Weight ratio	1.20871	0.838943
Reusability index	1.05	1

Tab. 2: Design summary of MEDIUM configuration (for the definitions of the parameters refer to ref. [7]) All values are given in SI units.

Fig. 7: Mass distribution MEDIUM configuration

Fig. 8: Outline of MEDIUM first stage

3.3 HEAVY configuration

The HEAVY configuration with 9 Prometheus engines in the first stage and 1 Prometheus engine in the second stage resulted in the design as detailed in Tab. 3. The definitions of the launcher parameters can be found in ref. [7]. The mass distribution is shown in Fig. 10.

The configuration can be summarized as follows:

- Design Payload: 8.1 t to GTO
- Payload to LEO (200 km): 33 t (estimated)
- Gross Lift-off Weight (GLOW): 877.61 t
- Thrust to Weight Ratio: 1.2
- Structural fraction dry
 - 6.0 % – stage 1
 - 5.8 % – stage 2

Fig. 9 shows the ascent trajectory of the HEAVY configuration. The stage separation takes place at an altitude of 77 km, at 2.0 km/s at a Mach number of 7.2 and a dynamic pressure of 59 Pa. With that the dynamic pressure is very low and the effect of aerodynamics after stage separation is negligible. The stage separation point is close to the one of the RETALT1 vehicle [18], which could provide a good comparability between both configurations.

Fig. 9: Ascent trajectory of HEAVY configuration

	Stage1	Stage2
Mass ratio	2.82169	8.98346
Stage mass share	0.752792	0.237922
Δv_i	3503.74	8285.15
Mass	660659	208803
Mass propellant ascent	566332	192725
Mass propellant descent	42474.9	0
Mass propellant total	608807	192725
Mass propellant reserve	6088.07	1927.25
Mass propellant dead	12176.1	3854.51
Mass payload	216866	8149.82
Mass gross real	877168	216843
Mass structure real wet	94327	16077.7
Mass structure real dry	39318.5	12113.1
Mass structure margin	3931.85	1211.31
Structural frac. real wet	0.142777	0.0769995
Structural frac. real dry	0.059514	0.0580121
Height	42.6457	29.5899
Outer diameter	5.4	5.4
Thrust (vacuum)	10994700	1312670
Thrust (sea level)	10316900	---
Thrust to Weight ratio	1.19935	0.61729
Reusability index	1.075	1

Tab. 3: Design summary of HEAVY configuration (for the definitions of the parameters refer to ref. [7]) All values are given in SI units.

Fig. 10: Mass distribution HEAVY configuration

The outline of the HEAVY configuration is shown in Fig. 11. The diameter was set to 5.4 m. Scaling the T3 aeroshape to this diameter results in the outline of HEAVY as shown in Fig. 11. The components and tanks fitted nicely into the geometry and the length scales were comparable to what was computed with AIOLOS in the design phase. Hence, the geometry was kept without further modifications. As the HEAVY configuration is a scaled T3 vehicle the aerodynamic coefficients are very comparable. Only the

engine cluster is changed, which consequently changes the aerodynamic coefficients slightly in the aerodynamic phase and more strongly in the burn phases.

Fig. 11: Outline of HEAVY first stage

4 DESCENT TRAJECTORIES

In the following the trajectories of the MEDIUM and HEAVY configurations will be compared with the T3 vehicle.

4.1 Similarity Parameters

In the aerodynamic phase mainly, the dynamic pressure is relevant for the structural loads. Therefore, this parameter is compared. The dynamic pressure q_∞ is defined as:

$$q_\infty = \frac{1}{2} \rho_\infty u_\infty^2 = \frac{1}{2} p_\infty M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty \quad (1)$$

with the density ρ_∞ , the static pressure p_∞ , the velocity u_∞ , the Mach number M_∞ and the heat capacity ratio γ_∞ .

During the re-entry burn the main similarity parameter to consider is the thrust coefficient [19-21] defined as follows:

$$C_T = \frac{F_T}{q_\infty A_{ref}} \quad (2)$$

with the thrust F_T , and the reference area A_{ref} , which in this case is the area of the base plane.

The Momentum Flux Ratio (MFR) is the similarity parameter mainly considered for the landing burn. It is defined as [22]:

$$MFR = \frac{\rho_e u_e^2}{\rho_\infty u_\infty^2} \quad (3)$$

Form eq. (3) follows with some transformations, that the MFR can also be computed from the vacuum thrust $F_{t,vac}$ (of a single engine), the engine exit area A_e and the dynamic pressure q_∞ with:

$$MFR = \frac{F_{t,vac} - A_e p_e}{2 q_\infty A_e} \quad (4)$$

If the pressure terms in the thrust are neglected the thrust coefficient can be written in terms of the MFR as follows [23, 24]:

$$C_T = 2 MFR \frac{A_e}{A_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

However, considering the pressure terms of the engine exit pressure (p_e) and free stream static pressure (p_∞) this would yield:

$$C_T = \underbrace{2 MFR \frac{A_e}{A_{ref}}}_{\text{thrust coefficient without pressure terms}} + \underbrace{\frac{p_e}{p_\infty} \frac{A_e}{\frac{1}{2} M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty A_B}}_{\text{engine exit pressure term}} - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty A_B}_{\text{static pressure term}} \quad (6)$$

Hence, the similarity of the thrust coefficient depends, additionally to the MFR, also on the exit pressure ratio p_e/p_∞ and on the free stream Mach number M_∞ .

In Fig. 12 the engine clusters of T3, MEDIUM and HEAVY are shown. Exemplarily, a UF2 configuration is highlighted with two white engine planes. It shall be noted here that, as the number of engines increases the ratio of the engine exit area A_e to the base area A_{ref} gets smaller. This affects the flow field even though the C_T -similarity is met. Furthermore, the engines in the HEAVY variant are further apart from each other which affects the plume-plume interaction and the interaction of the plumes with the freestream.

Fig. 12: Engine cluster of the T3 (left), MEDIUM (middle), HEAVY (right), UF2 configuration highlighted with two white engine exit planes.

The heat flux along the trajectory was estimated with the estimation by Sutton and Graves [25] which can be written in the form of [26]:

$$\dot{q} = 1.7414 \cdot 10^{-4} \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{R_n}} \cdot V^3 \quad (7)$$

where \dot{q} is the heat flux in W/m^2 , ρ is the density in kg/m^3 , R_n is the nose radius in m and V is the flight velocity in m/s . R_n was set to 0.5 m as proposed in [27]. However, due to the complex aeroshape with the engine clusters, landing legs and the grid fins, the heat flux on different parts of the vehicle are varying strongly. Furthermore, the approximation is not valid in the retro-propulsive phases. Hence, it only serves to

indicate an order of magnitude of the heat loads, and for a comparison between the vehicles, and is not representative for absolute values of the actual heat loads. A detailed analysis of the heat loads of T3 can be found in ref. [3].

4.2 MEDIUM configuration

The decent trajectory of the MEDIUM configuration is shown in Fig. 13. The trajectory was computed limiting the dynamic pressure to 120 kPa and to 100 kPa. It is interesting to note that when limiting the dynamic pressure to 120 kPa, no re-entry burn is necessary to achieve this value. If the dynamic pressure is limited to 100 kPa, only very short burn times are necessary. It was assumed, however, that the engines would have a minimum burn time of 5 s. Hence, the trajectory is dominated by this minimum burn time. Three trajectories were computed, with a re-entry burn with one, two or three active engines (R1, R2 and R3). For the landing burn one engine was used (L1).

The fuel consumption for all variants in ascending order is as follows:

- 120 kPa – R0L1: 4.3 t
- 100 kPa – R1L1: 5.7 t
- 100 kPa – R2L1: 7.2 t
- 100 kPa – R3L1: 8.7 t

Consequently, by setting the dynamic pressure limit to 120 kPa and omitting the re-entry burn saves the most fuel. With increasing number of engines in use for the re-entry burn, the fuel consumption increases. Note that all strategies are well within the limits of decent fuel assumed for the configuration which is 14 t.

In Fig. 14 the trajectories of the MEDIUM configuration are compared to the descent trajectory of T3. The re-entry burn of T3 is performed at considerably lower altitudes. Nevertheless, the dynamic pressure during the aerodynamic phase is rebuilt well.

Fig. 15 shows the comparison of the thrust coefficients of the T3 and the MEDIUM configuration along the trajectories excluding the landing burn. They are in a comparable range. For T3 the re-entry burn is assumed to be performed with two active engines here. Therefore, even though the re-entry burn is performed in lower altitudes, the similarity with the thrust coefficient should be well investigable.

The shown thrust coefficient is the total thrust coefficient. Hence, for T3, the thrust coefficient of a single engine is half of that value (as two engines are active). At the start of the re-entry burn the single engine thrust coefficient is 1.26. This is a quite low value and could be critical as for low thrust coefficients around 1 or lower a mode switch between the blunt mode and the long penetration mode can appear, which changes the flow field behaviour and the force and moment coefficients [19-21, 23]. A change of the flow field was indeed observed and is discussed in refs. [1, 5].

In Fig. 16 the trajectories and thrust coefficients are compared for the landing burn. In and Fig. 17 the thrust coefficients are plotted against the Mach numbers. For lower Mach numbers the dynamic pressure ultimately goes down to zero (due to zero velocity) and consequently the thrust coefficient increases to infinity. It can be seen that the Mach number and thrust coefficient range for the landing burn agree well between T3 and the MEDIUM configuration.

For the landing burn, the Momentum Flux Ratio (MFR) is the most important similarity parameter for comparison (see section 4.1). It is shown in Fig. 18 along the trajectory and in Fig. 19 versus the Mach number. The MFR agrees very well between the MEDIUM configuration and the T3 for all MEDIUM trajectories, especially the MFR versus the Mach number matches perfectly. This good agreement can be explained as follows. The MFR only depends on the nominal thrust (without pressure terms) divided by the dynamic pressure (see eq. (4)). As the landing burn occurs only over approx. 1.5 km, the changes in the static pressure are small, and as the dynamic pressure only depends on the static pressure, the Mach number and γ_∞ ($q_\infty = \frac{1}{2} \rho_\infty M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty$, see eq. (1)), the MFR over the Mach number must match, as the thrust and static pressure remain constant and hence the MFR only changes with the Mach number. This is an interesting finding, as it means that the similarity of the flow field for a certain thrust can be achieved independently of the trajectory. It is noticeable that the landing burn of the MEDIUM configuration starts at lower Mach numbers between 0.6 to 0.7 while it starts at around Mach 0.8 for T3.

In Fig. 20 the heat loads were estimated with Sutton-Graves as discussed in section 4.1. Fig. 20 shows the heat loads for the MEDIUM configuration and for T3 along the trajectories. Here instead of the Mach number, the velocity is plotted to show the trajectory, as it directly enters in eq. (7). Due to the relatively low velocities of T3, the heat loads are moderate with a peak of 126 kW/m². For the MEDIUM configuration the peak heat loads are as follows:

- 120 kPa – R0L1: 388 kW/m²
- 100 kPa – R1L1: 309 kW/m²
- 100 kPa – R2L1: 374 kW/m²
- 100 kPa – R3L1: 374 kW/m²

As the re-entry burn with one active engine starts at higher altitudes and reduces the maximum velocity in the aerodynamic phase it reduces the heat loads considerably. The maximum heat loads for R2 and R3 are the same as the re-entry burn is started just after the point of maximum velocity. The highest heat load is occurring (as expected) with no re-entry burn, as the velocities are the highest. However, the heat loads are still in an acceptable range.

From this analysis for the MEDIUM configuration, omitting the re-entry burn completely should be considered as the fuel consumption is the least, and the dynamic pressure and heat loads are acceptable. Using one engine, reduces the dynamic

pressure to the limit of 100 kPa and reduces the heat loads considerably with only a little increase in fuel consumption. The strategy of how many engines would be used would probably also depend on the mission (GTO or LEO and Down Range Landing or Return to Launch Site).

Fig. 13: Descent trajectory of the MEDIUM configuration

Fig. 15: Thrust coefficient of MEDIUM configuration compared with the T3 along the trajectories

Fig. 14: Descent trajectory of the MEDIUM configuration compared with the T3 trajectory

Fig. 16: Thrust coefficient along the trajectory of MEDIUM configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 17: Thrust coefficient versus Mach number of the MEDIUM configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 19: Momentum Flux Ratio versus Mach number of the MEDIUM configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 18: Momentum Flux Ratio along the trajectory of the MEDIUM configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 20: Heat flux of the MEDIUM configuration compared to T3

4.3 HEAVY configuration

Fig. 21 shows the descent trajectory of the HEAVY configuration. Here the same limits of 120 kPa and 100 kPa for the dynamic pressure were applied. The re-entry burn was performed with two or three active engines (R2 and R3). In this case the landing burn was always performed with three engines, as otherwise no valid solution for the descent trajectory was found. The trajectory optimization is, however, still ongoing and is going to be performed in detail by DEIMOS in the project.

It can be observed that the number of engines is not decisive for the aerodynamic phase. The optimization of the trajectory with the limit of the dynamic pressure yields basically the same dynamic pressure curve. However, performing the re-entry burn with only two engines shifts the burn to higher altitudes.

The fuel consumption for all variants in descending order is as follows:

- 100 kPa – R2L3: 29.7 t
- 100 kPa – R3L3: 28.8 t
- 120 kPa – R2L3: 26.6 t
- 120 kPa – R3L3: 26.2 t

This shows that increasing the allowable dynamic pressure to 120 kPa can save around 3 t of decent fuel. However, this of course comes with approximately 20% higher peak structural loads which is especially relevant for the aerodynamic control surfaces, but also for the general structural loads. Performing the re-entry burn with 2 instead of 3 engines can save approx. 1 t of fuel for the 100 kPa case. But for the 120 kPa case this saving is only about 0.4 t.

Therefore, for the decision which variant would be best, a trade-off is necessary considering various system aspects besides the fuel consumption.

Fig. 22 shows again a comparison of the HEAVY trajectory with the T3 trajectory. Also for this configuration, even though the re-entry burn takes place at lower altitudes for T3, the aerodynamic phase and the dynamic pressure curve is rebuilt well.

Fig. 23 shows again the comparison of the thrust coefficients of the HEAVY configuration and T3. As the re-entry burns of the HEAVY configuration take place at very high altitudes, the dynamic pressure is very low. Leading to very high thrust coefficients. This will lead to strongly under expanded plumes as could be seen in RETALT e.g. in ref. [26]. In comparison the T3 thrust coefficients are quite small. Therefore, for the re-entry burn, the T3 demonstrator shows a better representativity for the MEDIUM configuration than for the HEAVY configuration, as the MEDIUM configuration has lower thrust coefficients (see section 4.2). However, the general flow field phenomena of the re-entry burn can also be observed at lower thrust coefficients as shown in ref. [5] or also in experiments in the RETALT project in ref. [28, 29].

In Fig. 24 and Fig. 26 the trajectories, thrust coefficients and Momentum Flux Ratio are shown for the landing burn. It can be seen that, as for the MEDIUM configuration, the Mach number range, the thrust coefficient range and the range of Momentum Flux Ratio agree very well with the T3 configuration. This shows that there is a good reproducibility of the flight conditions at the landing burn of the full-scale vehicle with the demonstrator.

In Fig. 28 the heat flux, computed with Sutton-Graves, is shown for the T3 and the HEAVY configuration. The peak heat loads in descending order are:

- 120 kPa – R3L3: 351 kW/m²
- 100 kPa – R3L3: 327 kW/m²
- 120 kPa – R2L3: 275 kW/m²
- 100 kPa – R2L3: 205 kW/m²

Hence, the peak heat loads for the configurations with three active engines at the re-entry burn (R3) are much higher than with two engines (R2), as they start before the highest velocity parts of the trajectories. However, for all trajectory variants the heat loads are even a little bit lower than for the MEDIUM configuration. It should be noted that the lower thrust coefficient for the R3 trajectories (see Fig. 23) could potentially add to higher overall heat loads due to less effective shielding of the configuration during the re-entry burn with the plume as shown in ref. [3].

Fig. 21: Descent trajectory of the HEAVY configuration

Fig. 23: Thrust coefficient of the HEAVY configuration compared with the T3 along the trajectories

Fig. 22: Descent trajectory of the HEAVY configuration compared with the T3 trajectory

Fig. 24: Thrust coefficient of the HEAVY configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 25: Thrust coefficient versus Mach number of the HEAVY configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 27: Momentum Flux Ratio versus Mach number of the HEAVY configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 26: Momentum Flux Ratio of the HEAVY configuration compared with the T3 for the landing burn

Fig. 28: Heat flux of the HEAVY configuration compared to T3

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper the future launcher configurations studied in SALTO were presented.

The aim of this study is to assess the scalability of the technologies studied with the T3 vehicle to representative configurations of future launchers. For this reason, two configurations were presented in this paper which are, as T3, based on the Prometheus engine. The aeroshape of the configurations is closely derived from T3 to keep them as similar as possible for later comparison of the aerodynamic performance. The design ideas are derived from the MEDIUM and HEAVY configurations of Ariane Group from the ESA NESTS study.

It was shown that the aerodynamic phase is represented well with the T3 vehicle showing a similar dynamic pressure curve.

The thrust coefficients during the re-entry burn is in the same range for the MEDIUM and the T3 vehicle, for the HEAVY configuration the thrust coefficients are larger, as they are performed in higher altitudes and in lower dynamic pressures. For the MEDIUM configuration it was found that the re-entry burn could be omitted completely if the dynamic pressure limit is raised to 120 kPa.

For the landing burn the thrust coefficients and Mach numbers are in the same range for T3 and for the future launcher configurations. The Momentum Flux Ratios showed very good agreement. Therefore, with the T3 demonstrator the conditions of the landing burn could be reproduced very well for both future launcher configurations.

For the two future launcher configurations aerodynamic databases are currently being computed similar to the ones computed for T3 as presented in ref. [1]. However, as in SALTO only the first preliminary design loop of these configurations is performed, only low fidelity databases will be created. The databases will be used for the comparison of the aerodynamic performance of the future launcher configurations and the T3 vehicle in more detail. Additionally, together with the configuration design input they will serve for end to end flight mechanics analyses and mission analyses by DEIMOS. Furthermore, the structural integration of landing legs and aerodynamic control surfaces in the launcher structure is studied by MT Aerospace.

A similar study to the one presented here can be found in ref. [2], where the T3 vehicle trajectory is compared to those of Falcon 9 and RETALT and possible modifications to the T3 mission are highlighted to increase its representativeness.

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